

Linguistics in social-interactional perspectives: an overview of research

Language can be analyzed in different ways, especially because of the diversity of research methods and theoretical orientations in Linguistics and related areas. Nevertheless, in this special number, our focus is on approaches to language studies that center the notion of language from a social-interactional perspective. As Marcuschi (2009, p. 64) summarizes, language is “an activity, that is, a socio-interactive practice that is cognitively and historically grounded”. This idea is pivotal for the studies that are gathered in this special issue.

We understand that this notion of language runs through many theories and academic approaches. We thus acknowledge the importance of gathering papers that leverage nuanced language analyses in different contexts. The idea that brings about this number emerged from our own academic dialogue, stemming from the special editors' research interests. We share common ideas about what language is, although we focus on different perspectives, such as Interactional Sociolinguistics, Text Linguistics, Dialogic Discourse Analysis and Ethnography.

Therefore, this special issue gathers scholarly works that contribute in different ways to thinking about the relationship between language and society, centering socio-interactional notions of language. The theoretical and methodological orientations used in the articles of the special issue encompass studies on Text Linguistics, Discourse Analysis, Dialogic Theory of Language, Sociocognition, Textual-Interactive perspectives etc.

This diversity is also revealed in the applied field. The addressed topics include education, social media studies and work. Besides, socially relevant topics are also covered, such as racism, fat phobia, verbal violence, teaching and learning of languages and literature, representations of deafness etc. Thereupon, the issue promotes the discussion amongst different areas of language studies drawing upon nuanced observation, which emphasizes the co-construction of senses.

Our special issue begins with papers that are guided by different types of Discourse Analysis. Then, there are many works that follow contemporaneous perspectives on Text Linguistics. Next, the papers draw upon the multiple perspectives in Sociolinguistics and ethnographic research. This three-part division, however, does not account for the details that only the reading of each text is capable of showing. In order to provide a gist of these papers, we show a brief summary of each paper in the same order as displayed in the special issue.

In "*Contexto sob o viés da Sociocognição em livros didáticos de Língua Portuguesa*", Melo-Guimarães analyzes the contextual models activated in the opening sections of Portuguese

language textbooks for Brazilian elementary schools. Drawing on a socio-cognitive approach, the author unveils that the textbook aims at engaging the readers in an active reading process.

Ferraz and Silva investigate racial relations, leveraging the concept of whiteness, in "*Discurso jornalístico e as relações raciais: um olhar para a branquitude*". The authors draw on Discourse Analysis in order to study the journalistic discourse and conclude that the discourse of whiteness appears in the data subtly. Thus, discussions about racism and whiteness are silenced by the enunciators.

In the paper "*Slam: uma análise do discurso por meio das formações ideológicas e discursivas*", Souza, Azevedo e Albuquerque analyze the slam "*A menina que nasceu sem cor*". Taking the French Discourse Analysis as a reference, the article brings the resonance of prejudiced petrifications regarding blackness and it particularly shows the role of discursive resistance in this context.

Guedes, Oliveira, Barbuio and Lopes, in "*Linguagem, racismo, poder e carnavalização*", show the analysis of the "comic strip" journalistic genre based on the Dialogic Theory of Discourse. In the paper, they address concepts such as ideology, context, dialogism, carnivalization. The authors show that the use of carnivalization unveils racism and power relations in the society.

In "*Conceitos bakhtinianos na compreensão do texto literário: dialogismo e plurilinguismo como princípios de construção do sentido*", Fernandes and Barreto Filho address some concepts of Bakhtin's theory in the process of reading comprehension of literary texts, from the analysis of a didactic activity. The authors argue that one can work with reading in classes of French as a foreign language by considering dialogic aspects of comprehension.

Assis and Couto, in "*Um possível diálogo entre a Linguística da Enunciação e a Ecolinguística*", address the relationship between enunciative theories, with emphasis on Bakhtin and Benveniste, and Ecolinguistics. The authors verify the relationship between the fields, but point out that Ecolinguistics, or Ecosystemic Linguistics, propose re-elaborations of some concepts.

Dornelas, Farias and Mamani discuss the daily resistance of migrant women in the article "*Identidades linguísticas e resistências cotidianas de mulheres migrantes no Brasil*". Their study is based on the linguistic-discursive analysis of migrant women's reports about their experiences in Brazil and seeks to unveil the challenges they faced related to the language.

Leite and Morais, in "*Jornalismo no Twitter: uma análise discursiva de destacamentos no jornal Folha de São Paulo*", analyze news in the format of Twitter threads. Drawing on the French Discourse Analysis, they seek to find the differences and similarities in the utterances that went

through the process of *detachment* in the in-press and digital journalism. They thus verified the prevalence of the framing of impartiality and exemption.

In "*TikTok: possibilidades de gestos críticos no ambiente virtual*", Pereira and Silva reflect upon how the discourses in TikTok stimulate and contribute to the (de)construction of ideological positioning. Drawing on dialogic perspectives of language, digital discourse analysis and critical literacy, the paper argues that the analyzed social networking website contributes to performative discourses of social facts and topics.

In "*A contingência da coerência à luz da noção de contexto: análise de tuites do Globo Rural*", Santana and Marques draw on Text Linguistics to explain the processes of construction of coherence in digital interactions in the official webpage of a TV show. Based on the notion of context and its categories of emergency and incorporation, the authors observed how the incorporation of an interaction to more than one context can be strategic to generate engagement in digital interactions, emphasizing the ambivalent character of the tweet between the fields of politics and agro-business.

In the article "*Perspectiva Textual-Interativa e Plurissemiotividade: discussão sobre alcance e limite com base em um estudo bibliométrico*", by Pinheiro and Lima, they notice that their research topic is rarely explored in academia. The authors get to this conclusion after a bibliometric study of theses and dissertations of graduate programs in Languages and Linguistics in Brazil. They show that there is the use of principles and categories from the Textual-Interactive Perspective in plurisemiotic studies, but there is no theoretical formalization and analytical procedures to the coherent application of these categories.

Fat phobia is addressed by Vasconcelos, Bernardino and Queiroz in the article "*A gordofobia no gênero notícia em uma análise textual-discursiva da representação discursiva e da responsabilidade enunciativa*". The authors ground their study in the Textual Discourse Analysis and the Theory of Point of View, focusing on semantic-pragmatic, enunciative and socio-discursive dimensions. In a news article about an episode of fat phobia published in *Claudia* magazine, in February of 2020, they analyze the discursive representation manifestation and the enunciative responsibility assumption, considering the management of points of view in the text by the first locutor-enunciator.

Rocha's research, in the article "*A construção da narrativa em textos produzidos por estudantes com e sem TDAH*", verifies comparatively the development in the production of narratives of two groups of students in Brazilian elementary schools. The first group includes

students who have Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and the second group includes students who have high levels of attention and do not have ADHD. The author analyzes aspects of the construction and organization of the text in order to verify differences between the production of these two groups. She draws on the literature about ADHD, in the studies about texts and language practices and in the structure of narrative by Labov and Waletzky.

In "*Educar crianças em línguas adicionais para a diversidade e justiça social: contribuições sociointeracionais do gênero história infantil*", Magiollo and Tonelli suggest a didactic sequence for additional language learning with students in the first grade of a public Brazilian elementary school. This didactic sequence systematizes the relation between the "stories" genre for children, the narrative and character system, and the choice of topics related to the principles of education for social justice. The collected data show that the text genre was used by the students as a space for identity construction, while the English language was a tool for social interaction.

In the article "*Seleção lexical e construção da argumentatividade em textos do domínio jornalístico*", Neves collected opinionated texts from newspapers in Pernambuco (Brazil) that were published during the second round of the presidential election in 2018 about this topic. By analyzing the lexical items used in these texts, the author explained how the words functioned as contextualization cues of the argumentative positions taken by columnists and editors of newspapers in Pernambuco. In general, the results convey a strong relationship amongst the text genre, the authors, and the choice of lexical items related to the topic discussed by the texts.

Arraz, in the article "*Gíria dos acautelados: recurso linguístico dos jovens que se encontram privados de liberdade*", studies slang, which are seen as a way for protection and identification. He addresses the slang used by a group of adolescents and youngsters that are deprived of freedom. According to the study, these users have the need to create a linguistic sign that is adequate to the goal of seeking closeness with whom they talk to, and also to produce meaning that other words would not create.

In Pelayes and Cavalcante's article, "*Processos de reparo: uma análise de atitudes linguísticas em vídeo humorístico do Tik Tok*", they work with the phenomenon of repair in the interpretation of correction in talk-in-interaction. The authors relate this phenomenon to linguistic prejudice and analyze a video that was published in a TikTok webpage. Pelayes and Cavalcante conclude that social media can act as tools to disseminate the notion of mistake, sometimes humorously, and these practices might strengthen some types of prejudice, including the linguistic one.

Albuquerque and Souza, in the article "*Gente, temos um gênio aqui: a coconstrução da violência linguístico-discursiva em uma interação no Twitter*", analyze the impoliteness strategies in the promotion of mutual linguistic-discursive violence between two internet users who comment on a post in the Twitter account of the Brazilian Ministry of Health. As their theoretical framework, the authors articulate the studies on (im)politeness, inscribed in the micro/linguistic, macro/socio-discursive and meso/social-interactional domains, and the study of argumentation with emphasis on the eristic argumentation because of its intrinsic relation to linguistic-discursive violence.

In the article "*A representação social sobre o surdo: um estudo de caso*", the analysis of the social representation of deaf people makes Menezes and Barros study the Theory of Social Representation by Moscovici and his disciples. The authors position the (re)construction of social representation as a complex cognitive process that has social marks.

Besides the 19 articles, there are 3 other texts of different academic genres in this issue: one book review and two interviews. The scientific discussion in different genres - other than research papers - reinforces the multiple characteristics of language and, in a comprehensive way, exemplifies how research approaches are diverse.

In the book review "*Discussão sobre a prática escolar de análise linguística em perspectiva dialógica*", Neves, Lima, Gomes and Oliveira discuss the book "*Prática de análise linguística nas aulas de língua portuguesa*", organized in 2021 by Rodrigo Acosta and Terezinha Costa-Hübes. The reviewers formulate an overview of research on the practice of linguistic analysis in Basic Education, considering one social-interactional perspective: the dialogic approach to language.

In the interview "The social-interactional perspectives in the studies of special education and autism: an interview with Kristen Bottema-Beutel and Juliene Madureira Ferreira", Lima Becker and Barreto Filho address the affordances and challenges of social-interactional research on special education and autism through the interviewees' experiences. The interview shows their research works, which display the agency, affordances and capacities of students with disabilities.

In the interview "*Observações sobre os estudos linguísticos em perspectivas sociointeracionais no Brasil: uma conversa com Anna Christina Bentes*", Neves, Fernandes, Silva and Figueiredo present a conversation they had with Dr Anna Bentes from Unicamp. Based on different topics, the interview provides an overview of Brazilian interactional studies, placing it in a more comprehensive theoretical-methodological context. They bring many examples and explanations that clearly illustrate the meaning of studying language from an interactional perspective.

The range of research studies displayed in this special issue, with 3 different genres and a myriad of theories of language studies, allows the reader to be in contact with a sample of what has been worked contemporaneously in Brazil in terms of social-interactional perspective. We hope to contribute to this discussion in Brazilian Linguistics and generate dialogues amongst researchers who aim at understanding the relationship between language and its exteriority by the means of this special issue of *Revista Letras Raras*.

References

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